

ANTHROPONYMS-AS A SOCIO-HISTORICAL LINGUISTIC TOOL

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Abstract. *Anthroponyms, which are considered a separate layer of onomastic science that studying names, are considered an important part of human identification and culture, differing in specific system that individual names are formed such as name-middle name-surname, and represent the national identity of people. Individual names are formed and develop under the influence of national traditions of each People, economic factors in society and important historical events. Therefore, the evolution of names often reflects significant changes in society, from historical-social, religious changes to political ideologies and global trends. This article is aimed at highlighting the importance of names as a socio-historical and cultural phenomenon of universal and at the same time national characteristics inherent in each language, in which anthroponyms are considered as linguistic elements that reflect cultural, religious, historical and social changes in society. The article analyzes the multifaceted role of anthroponyms in reflecting social change on the example of naming practices in Uzbek, English and Russian. In particular, the national-cultural characteristics in Uzbek, the religion of Islam, Soviet ideology and the fact that new values formed in the period of Independence played an important role in the evolution of names were facilitated by examples. Also, through examples, information on periodization in the languages being compared, features of socio-historical names associated with them were distinguished, the main factors affecting the popularization of names were identified and their dynamics were analyzed.*

Keywords: *onomastics, anthroponyms, person names, naming, functional changes, socio-historical, cultural, religious, political-ideological, economic and social action factors.*

In society, each thing has its own term, among which the special distinction of certain objects, individuals creates a layer of proverbial nouns. The words of this layer are studied in the so-called onomastics section of linguistics. Based on the fact that everything surrounding us can have its own name, onomastic layers cover all languages, all geographical and cultural regions and all historical periods. It is worth noting that initially not everything in existence had its own name, however, nowadays it has become common to name everything in existence-objects, events-phenomena separately from each other. On the other hand, the naming process is not spontaneous. In times when people did not know how to think fully, did not think enough about phenomena, they could not give a clear and correct name to what is in existence. When a particular object or person is named, its appearance, characteristics, color, taste, geographical origin are also partially taken into account and named.

In particular, personal names, which are an integral part of every person's life, have attracted the attention of researchers as part of the language system for a long time. As a result of this interest, a special branch of onomastics – anthroponymy, which studies the names of individuals developed. An individual is personified by birth with a separate name and surname. In

each nation, naming a child is a linguistic activity that takes into account psychological, social and cultural factors that change and develop under the influence of historical, political, economic, religious and cultural factors. It follows from this that the name of each person serves as a specific part of particular culture, and at the same time a personal name itself is a product of national culture. As A.V. Superanskaya noted, " the place of a personal name in a person's life is huge. Everyone can only be called by name, so all his good and bad deeds are made public thanks to his name"[1]

The objects of study of anthroponymy are personal names, the naming system itself, individuals, identification of names, name – middle name – surname systems, as well as nicknames, pennames; and this system studies the functions of names in speech, age-related, social or marital status, temporary (short or long) migration, changes in citizenship, changes associated with the adoption of another religion, etc.

The placement of names is often associated with nature and professions, the socio-economic cultural lifestyle of a particular people, including the Uzbek people who practiced agriculture and handicrafts in their way of life are associated with the terms nature, plants, various trades, and in the Kazakh, Turkmen, Kyrgyz peoples who practiced livestock, names associated with animals are common.

The origin and development of names were also greatly influenced by religious-ideological factors at different times. It is argued that while the introduction of Islam in Central Asia led to the popularization of Arabic names, Christianity in Europe was the reason for the widespread use of biblical names. Also, historical events such as colonialism and warfare are featured in the names, and the processes of urbanization and globalization have resulted in a diversity of naming practices and the emergence of hybrid and gender-specific names. Above mentioned statements also show the importance of studying anthroponyms not only as a linguistic and national-cultural phenomenon, but also as a socio-historical phenomenon that reflects various stages of the life of society.

Individual names are not only isolated, distinct linguistic elements in any language or its naming art, but they also form an anthroponymic system that always includes several different subsystems. These subsystems include, for example, the name system and surname system of European languages, or the clan name system of some African languages (a clan is a unit formed by several families who identify themselves as descended from the same, often mythical ancestors; each clan has its own name, reflecting its own characteristics) can be an example. Thus, each language has an anthroponymic system, but what subsystems it consists of is characteristic of the culture of those linguists. Individual, personal names are not the result of creating a word to name another object of reality, it is a necessity for human existence for thousands of years. It is not a simple linguistic concept, but a unit of language with spiritual value. Therefore, at present, the problem of the concept of personal names and its state in the lexical system is considered very relevant and interesting.

In the 19th and 20th centuries, many scholars considered personal names to be simply a deictic marker, a unit that serves to indicate and identify identity. In modern research, anthroponymy is approached as a sign that expresses reality and exists in it, depending on linguistic, cultural and social factors. In some studies, anthroponyms are classified into two main groups: individual and collective. Including A.V. Superanskaya's view, " Individual names distinguish an individual from a community, while collective names are assigned to communities

that stand out on the basis of certain characteristics (common, family, dynastic names)”[2]. Obviously, as she noted, "the place of a name in a person's life is very great. Everyone can only be called by name, so all his good and bad deeds are made public thanks to his name "[3].

D.A. Yermolovich has described anthroponyms as one of the classes of nouns, words, and phrases "officially assigned to a person as his identification mark"[4] noting the existence of various forms of naming, such as their person's names, surnames, nicknames. In each language, this lexical layer contains the national cultural information of this Ethnos and at the same time, reflects the socio-historical changes and the worldview of the people to whom they belong. Therefore, research in this area is always relevant, and their relevance is growing more and more. It seems that in each language, anthroponymic systems are derived from the culture of Ethnos or nations, who are considered the owners of that language. Therefore, in the study of anthroponyms, it will be necessary to study them not only as linguistic units, but also as a socio-historical linguistic tool that reflects changes in society.

Whereas 19th-20th-century scholars considered personal names to be merely a deictic character, a unit that serves to indicate and identify identity, in modern research anthroponymy is approached as a character that reflects reality from linguistic, cultural and social factors. Seeing this on the example of the Uzbek people, the practice of Uzbek naming has undergone major changes due to socio-political, cultural and religious changes. During the analysis of events that made significant changes in the life of society, we analyzed the states of their reflection in anthroponyms and studied the influence of important periods on anthroponyms. Based on the results of the research work studied, we have classified the main periods in the history of Turkic peoples and their impact on naming practices as follows:

Table 1.1

The main periods in the history of Turkic peoples and their influence on naming practices

Periods	Special features in naming	Examples	Investigated scholars
Pre-Islamic era	Names associated with animals, courage or nature; Turkic tribal names	<i>Kuchkar</i> <i>Boru</i> <i>Alpomish</i> <i>Oguzkhan</i>	N.A. Baskakov[5] V.G. Bondaletov[6]
Islamic era	Adoption of Arabic Islamic names; hybridization with Turkic names	<i>Muhammad</i> <i>Abdullah</i> <i>Aisha Fatima</i>	S.I. Zinin[7] R.B. Suleymonov[8]
The Timurid era	The restoration of Turkic national pride; names with deep meaning and reflecting leadership.	<i>Amirkhan</i> <i>Temurbek</i> <i>Ulugbek</i>	Khalid[9] D.I. Yermolovich[10]
Soviet era	Secular and ideological names; limiting Islamic naming practices.	<i>Oktyabrina</i> <i>Stalina</i> <i>Saodat</i> <i>Kahraman</i>	V.A. Nikonov[11]

Post-independence period	revival of Islamic and historical names; emphasis on national cultural identity.	<i>Babur</i> <i>Azadbek</i> <i>Shakhsanam</i> <i>Sevara</i>	Khalid[12]
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Anthroponyms that are considered an important part of personality-specific names, human identity, and culture serve as linguistic markers that reflect social, historical, cultural, and religious changes in society. Names are not only a personal identity, but also a unique resource that embodies traditions, values and historical experiences, illuminating the interconnection between society and culture. The study of cultural, religious, political, economic and historical factors shows that anthroponyms are not only linguistic elements, but also a means of shaping the national self, reflecting religious, ideological, cultural changes in society. In each language, individual names change depending on socio-historical changes in society. Significant changes can be seen in the evolution of names in different languages, from religious changes in society to political ideologies and global trends. It seems that the origin and development of names were also greatly influenced by religious-ideological factors at different times. Let us dwell on the factors affecting anthroponyms below:

Picture 1.
Factors affecting the naming practice

I. National-cultural factors. As you know, each nation is distinguished by its national-cultural ethnic characteristics. National-cultural characteristics are derived from the way of life, customs, values of peoples, and they are manifested in the way people communicate, moral standards, live, and are also reflected in the onomastic layer of the lexicon of the same folk language. In particular, the names used in the farming Uzbek people are more associated with nature, plants, seasons, days (e.g. *Gulbahor, Gulchehra, Aydin, Oftob, Jumagul, Payshanba, Bozorboy, Chori, Panja*), related to handicrafts, field labor (e.g., *Dehkanbay, Urakbay, Tesha, Boltabay*), animal-related names are more common in cattle-breeding peoples (e.g., *Burivoy, Sherali, Ganisher, Sherzod, Tulpar, Kuchkar*). There are also names associated with names of festivals (such as *Hayitgul, Hayitboy, Navruz, Arafat*), with names of great ancestors (such as *Temur, Babur, Manguberdi*).

National-cultural identity can also be observed in names for twin children in different peoples. In the Uzbek people, it was usually required that male twins be named *Hassan* and *Hussan*, and female twins *Fatima* and *Zuhra*. Even children born after twin children are given the names *Tokhir (Toir)* if there is a boy, *Zokhir (Zoir)* to the next, *Tokhira, Zakhro* to the girls.

However, we do not observe this practice in most peoples, including English-speaking peoples. Unlike Uzbek customs, English-speaking parents often choose twin names based on phonetic harmony or thematic associations. For example, twins may be called *Lily* and *Rose* (both flower names) or *Jack* and *Jill*. However, there is no strictly defined tradition or cultural basis in naming twins, and this gives parents more freedom to choose a name for twins.

It seems that national-cultural characteristics are fully reflected in anthroponyms, where language occupies an important place in the onomastic layer of vocabulary wealth. How human patronym, first name, mathronym and forms of expression of surnames come from both form and content from national calorite. Including the plurality of nouns in Chinese, Korean, Japanese (such as *King Nan Ji, Wang Wei Ling, Kim Ji-hoon, or Tanaka Haruto*), the completion in *Georgian* with the -dze part, in *Armenian* with the -yan part (such as *Georgadze, Grigoryan, Shavidze, Macharashvili, Beridze, Sarkisyan, Arakelyan or Hovhannisyen*), the addressing in *Russian*, -ovich, -yevna forms (such as *Semen Semenovich, like Olga Viktorovna, Nikolay Konstantinovich, Natalia Petrovna or Dmitry Sergeevich*), the presence of parts of *ibn, Abu* in *Arabic* names (e.g. *Ibn Khattab*, Factors such as *Abu Zubayda, Abu Bakr, Ibn Abbas, Abdullah ibn Umar*) clearly show national cultural characteristics. These factors also influence naming practices through intermarriage, colonization, or migration through contact with other cultures in the process of cultural assimilation. The historical changes that occur in society also lead to cultural changes, and they are also manifested in anthroponyms. In particular, due to the introduction of Islam into Central Asia, the prevalence of Arabic names in Turkic peoples, and Russian patronymic system after the period of Russification, even cases of giving Russian names to a child in families whose mother is Russian, are very common.

II. Religious factors. The adoption of new religious systems often leads to changes in naming conventions. For example, the spread of Arabic names such as *Abu Rayhan, Abu ali ibn Sino, Muhammad Musa Al-Khwarazmi* to Central Asia after the arab conquest due to Islamization, the emergence of Uzbek names containing Persian or Arabic elements is clear evidence of this. Or as a consequence of Christianization, anglo-Saxon names such as *Dickattelred* were replaced in Medieval England by Biblical and Saint names such as *John* and *Mary*. Names become a means of religious identity, which indicates dependence on a particular belief. N. A. Baskakov studies

the influence of Islamization on middle Asian names, noting that the spread of Islam has led to "a significant addition of arab anthroponyms to the Turkic language circle reflecting religious and moral qualities" replacing pre-Islamic Turkic names with Arabic ones after the Arab conquest. In his view, names such as *Mukhammad*, *Ali*, and *Aisha* embodied piety and moral values, gradually pushing out animistic and shamanistic traditions. The scientist notes that under the influence of these social changes, that is, due to the integration of Islamic and Persian naming systems into Turkic languages, in particular among Uzbeks, 3 stages of naming: the pre-Islamic era, the Islamic era and the Soviet era came to existence, naming trends in the Soviet era reflected ideological changes, and religious designations decreased sharply.

We think that it is advisable to periodize the names of the current Uzbek language as follows:

1. Names from pre-Islamic times. Names such as *Buri*, *Kaldirgach*, *Kuchkar*, reflecting nature and animistic beliefs during this period;

2. Names of the Islamic period. During this period, Arabic names such as *Mukhammad*, *Abdullah*, *Fatima*, *Aisha*, *Mastura* and Persian names such as *Zebo*, *Gulshan*, *Saltanat*, *Khonzodabegim*, *Zebuniso*, *Shakhrizada*;

3. Soviet-era designations. Names such as *Ernest*, *Stalina*, *Oktyabrina*, representing the Soviet regime and ideology during this period; names such as *Marat*, *Svetlana*, *Vadik*, *Muratik*, *Alik*, which were influenced by Russification; names such as *Barno*, *Ra'no*; secular names like *Saida*, *Nadira*, *Gulzoda*, *Batir*, *Bakhtiyar*, *Pulat*, *Utkir*, *Alisher*;

4. Names of the period of independence. This period saw the rise of religious-ideological names such as *Gulnoza*, *Shakhnoza*, *Sevara*, *Saadat*, *Jakhangir*, *Jasur*, *Azamat* and *Mukhammadali*, *Nurmukhammad*, *Medina*, *Iymana*, *Amina*.

In English, too, the names are periodized in their own way. David Crystal analyzes how anglo-Saxon designations were changed during Christianization, noting that after the Roman mission to England, names such as *Æthelredka* and *Beowulf* were replaced by names in the "Bible" such as *John*, *Mary* and *Elizabeth*. In his view, this shift served as a symbol of harmony with Christian Europe, and names were often chosen to honor saints or events in the Christian calendar. At the same time as the reforms, religious upheavals led to the further spread of Names containing Protestant ideals: *Peter* (who was one of the apostles of Jesus), *Poole* (inspired by St. Paul, the main figure of the New Testament), *Faith* (one of the 3 divine virtues), *James* (derived from the famous apostle St. James), *Hope* (a name based on another virtue).

III. Political and ideological factors. Anthroponyms also reflect political and ideological changes. O. A. Leonovich who studied the influence of ideological designations of the Soviet period on Uzbek names, noted in his monograph that such designations as *Vilena* (short for Vladimir Il'ich Lenin), *Mels* (short for Marx, Engel's, Lenin, Stalin's names), *Stalin*, *Oktyabrina* served to personally identify and align the leaders of the October Revolution with socialist values. He believed that these traditional names were popularized under the secularization policies of the Soviet regime, and that "naming conventions of the Soviet era reflected the ideological priorities of the state, placing secular and revolutionary values above religious or traditional values".

V. A. Nikonov, also focusing on the reflection of the ideology of the Soviet period in anthroponyms, notes that in this naming practice, anthroponyms often became "propaganda tools" celebrating political leaders and achievements at the expense of traditional naming systems: "the

Soviet regime used names to ensure ideological control, replacing religious and aristocratic names with secular ones”.

After the victory of the Patriotic War in 1945, names such as *Golib, Muzaffar, Bahadir, Zafar, Sadakat, Shukrullo, Shavkat, Kahraman*, and upon independence, our own values and national-cultural values began to be reflected in names, and names such as *Azadbek, Islambek, Marifaat, Adalat, Nurbek, Saodat* began to become popular. O. A. Leonovich analysed the post-independence period in which traditional names such as *Timur* and *Ulughbek* were revived in Uzbekistan, stating that “the revival of traditional Uzbek names after 1991 represents a cultural awakening and a renunciation of Soviet-era influences”. This shift deliberately excluded Soviet-imposed names from circulation, symbolizing cultural pride and the restoration of national identity.

David Crystal, also studying the features of the imposition and distribution of English names during the world wars, notes that “it was during this period that patriotic names such as *Victoria* and *Hope* increased”. This process can also be observed on the example of other languages. In particular, in Russian, such names as *Bratislava, Slava, Victor* became popular, and these names became the embodiment of national heroism and optimism. Also, the names honoring soldiers killed in the war or commemorating peace movements have become traditional. It seems that in the placement and popularization of names a particular society is also influenced by political-ideological factors.

IV. Economic and social action factor. Socio-economic changes in the life of society, reforms in industry and production also affect the designations. The industrial reform of the 50s and 60s led to the emergence of such names in Uzbek as *Pulat, Temir, Sanoat, Norpulat*.

As you know, England is considered the hearth of the Industrial Revolution. This deeply shaped English naming practices, not just the industry and manufacturing sector. During the Industrial Revolution, English surnames became the identifier of the pulpit, reflecting social shifts towards labor specialization. Crystal argues that surnames such as *Smith, Carpenter, and Miller* became more common and represent the importance of these professions in social identity. These occupational names often became surnames and served as a mark of identity for generations.

The rise of globalization has diversified name practices in English-speaking countries. Patrick Hanks studied the evolution of English naming systems, highlighting the impact of global migration and media, and categorized the English names into:

- a) traditional names - names based on the Biblical or royal history (like *John, Elizabeth*).
- b) modern names - names that are influenced by pop culture and globalization (like *Arya, Kay*).

Patrick Hanks states that “global migration and media influence have changed English naming practices that incorporate elements of non-European cultures”. N.A. Baskakov also notes that urbanization has led to a simplification of traditional names such as the reduction of the name *Abdurahman* to *Rahman*, with these changes reflecting the needs of bureaucratic efficiency and modern communication. In Uzbek, this phenomenon is reflected in the use of *Gulchekhra* as *Guli*, *Aynisa* as *Nisa*, *Raziyabanu* as *Banu*, *Mukhammad Rakhim* as *Mamarayim*, *Mukhammad Karim* as *Matkarim*, *Mukhammad Ali* as *Mamadali* forms.

Anthroponyms often serve as expressions of social movements. The shift from rural traditions to urban naming reflected economic and social adaptation. David Crystal studied the proliferation of gender-independent names such as *Taylor, Jordan, and Morgan* in English. Crystal

argues that “the emergence of gender-neutral names reflects broader social trends towards inclusiveness and equality”.

These names reflect evolving attitudes towards gender equality and inclusion, provide flexibility, and undermine traditional gender diversity. Even in the life of the Uzbek people, especially after independence, efforts to urbanize them increased by reducing the gap between the village and the city, creating conditions for the economic development of villages. These urbanization movements also affected names, designations. Common names among rural populations such as *Teshavoy*, *Jumavoy*, *Payshanba*, *Bazarbay*, *Rizvan*, *Tukhtasin*, *Tukhta*, *Tursunay*, *Turgun*, *Tulagan*, *Talib*, *Turdi*, *Turdigul*, *Khabiba*, *Khalima*, *Salima*, *Mastura*, *Mamlakat*, *Kumri*, *Umrinisa*, *Khakima* were replaced with the names that were popular in urban areas such as *Shakhla*, *Barna*, *Dono*, *Nargiza*, *Gulnoza*, *Nodira*, *Nigina*, *Yulduz*, *Jasur*, *Javlon*, *Jahongir*, *Alisher*, *Otabek*, *Durbek*, *Ulugbek*, *Ozoda*, *Doniyor*, *Davron*, *Ziyoda*, *Lola*, *Dildora*, *Diyora*, *Rukhshona*.

V. Historical factors. Historical events are reflected in anthroponyms in all languages and leave a deep mark. While N.A Baskakov and I.S. Chursina were studying the influence of arab invasions on Central Asian names, they note that “pre-Islamic Turkic names such as *Boru* have been replaced by Islamic names such as *Hassan* and *Fatima*”. In addition to the names that reflect the heritage and historical personalities of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to note the significant changes caused by Russification in the formation of names. Russian patronymic forms such as -ov, -ova, -ev became popular. In addition, O.A. Leonovich notes that during migration conflicts “hybrid naming practices reflect the interaction of traditional identity and external factors in times of crisis”. It brought into circulation hybrid names such as *Danielbek*, *Svetlana*, *Mary*, *Sabrina*, *Ferdinand*, combining Uzbek and foreign elements

In English, David Crystal argued that colonial expansions influenced the practice of naming by including names tied to imperial power such as Victoria and George. In his view, “the impact of World Wars on English naming conventions shows a deep connection between historical events and personal identity”. These names signified loyalty to the British Empire, but post-colonial resistance witnessed the revival of local names in former colonies reflecting cultural melioration. In Uzbek, however, global media has spawned unconventional names, such as *Alina* or *Diana*, which harmonize different cultures, especially among the urban population.

The results of the study show that names are not only a personal identity, but also a rich heritage that embodies the historical and cultural experiences of the people. The evolution of Uzbek names shows that it was formed through national-cultural values, the influence of Islam, Soviet ideology and new values of the period of independence. Religious, political and economic factors also played a decisive role in names in English and Russian. Also, the processes of globalization and urbanization have increased diversity in anthroponyms, leading to the formation of neutral and hybrid names for the new gender. From this study, it is established that anthroponyms are not only a means of reflecting the language and culture of their time, but also a part of social progress. Through names, it is emphasized that there is an opportunity to restore national identity and preserve cultural heritage. The results presented in the article set the stage for a more thorough study of anthroponyms in Uzbek, English and Russian, and reveal their cultural and linguistic significance, and show that anthroponyms are an important linguistic tool that reflects social, cultural, religious and political changes in society.

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